

Alligator Method

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Abstract. This short paper describes the "Alligator" Method, which converts the results of a CA into a relative chronology following Allen's interval algebra. This enables temporal reasoning and visualisation in graphs or timelines, as well as the export in standards such as RDF.

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1 CORRESPONDENCE ANALYSIS AND AGT FILE

As the starting point (Step A), an "AGT-file" is used comprising the values: (a) name, xyz-coordinates, start / end dates (if available) and (b) uncertainty information about "fixed" absolute dates / "floating" endings. This file is generated from the correspondence analysis output in which the quantitative relations of the Euclidean distances between finds and proposed time intervals are calculated.

Following the "horseshoe paradigm", the CA result may provide a measure of (possible chronological) overlap between the Limes intervals. It is important to note that a CA does not comprise any pre-known dating information. Therefore, the AGT-file is enhanced with dating metadata (start / end dates, uncertainty information).

2 ALLIGATOR ALGORITHM

The “Alligator Algorithm” starts with 3D distance calculations (Step B) using the coordinates of the first 3 CA dimensions. Then the “Alligator Algorithm” calculates undated wobbly floating periods by finding the next 3D CA neighbour (Step C). Following this, the new virtual time intervals are calculated, and the resulting “virtual fuzzy years” (Step D) are generated based on Allen’s interval algebra. Any resulting “virtual fuzzy year” is then transformed into relative intervals and stored in RDF format where all the initial and calculated results, as well as the Allen intervals, are stored (Step E). This is the basis for visualisation, e.g. as a graph or a timeline (Step F).

Each relation contains a degree of connection that is based on the rules of vagueness. In the case of the AMT approach, we have to transform the intervals into AMT format and include the degree of connection, e.g. as a (normalised) Pearson correlation coefficient (Step G). This RDF file (Step H) serves as input for the AMT. With AMT, temporal reasoning (Step I) according to the specific ontology can be calculated, and afterwards exported and visualised (Step J).

Figure 1: The Alligator Method in 10 steps. [Florian Thiery, Allard W. Mees / LEIZA, CC BY 4.0]

Figure 2: The horseshoe paradigm for temporal entities [Florian Thiery, Allard W. Mees / LEIZA, CC BY 4.0, after Madsen 1988, Fig. 11; Madsen, T. 1988. Multivariate statistics and archaeology. In: Madsen, T. (ed.), *Multivariate Archaeology. Numerical Approaches in Scandinavian Archaeology*. Jutland Archaeological Society Publications 21, 7-28.]